

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MBINKAR BERINYUY****FIRST NAME: ANDREW****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2021 on Macbook Air)

5 key concepts with page number in text

1. Definition of an academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 7)
2. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2024, 8)
3. Organization of ideas (EUCLID 2024, 9)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 41)

STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF AN ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

With the advent of social media, writing down personal reflections and long texts has become a challenge. This accounts for why some students prefer audio or video presentations to writing a paper. The challenge of writing is seen even in ordinary communication on social media. Many students find it easier to use abbreviations, shorthand writing, and emojis to communicate. All this contributes to making an academic paper writing a difficult task.

Academic papers are indispensable in higher education. Through academic papers, students communicate the fruit of their research and demonstrate their understanding of the course. **An academic paper, according to EUCLID (2024, 7)**, is a nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic papers are “research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monograph; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students’ presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above” (EUCLID 2024, 7). Good academic papers respect academic rules. Given the importance of academic papers, it will be helpful for students to be aware of what strengthens and

weakens academic papers. Drawing inspiration from EUCLID (2024), I will bring out some of the strengths and weaknesses of academic papers.

2) STRENGTHS OF AN ACADEMIC PAPER

a) Clarity of the topic

The topic of every academic paper is like the door through which the reader can access the whole body of the research. In most cases, the topic announces already what will be read in the body of the essay. The subject matter of an essay should synthetically be reflected in the topic. Therefore, the topic must be clear enough to help the reader know what to expect in that connection. The topic should also incite the curiosity of the reader to read on. Given that the topic plays a key role in the whole paper, the student will need to choose a topic that is relevant and which he is passionate about. In order not to choose just any topic, Cleenewerck & Gulma (2024, 8) suggest the following questions that could help the student in their choice of the topic: “What do I already know about the topic? What do I need to read and know to write the essay? Is this material useful to my topic?” Consequently, the choice of a topic should reflect what the writer cares about and what they already know or intend to learn about.

b) Plan of work

Before the construction of a house begins, the builders take sufficient time to carve out the plan. The plan of the house reflects the final product they have in their minds and the step-by-step process they need to take to get to that final product. Similarly, an academic paper requires a plan. A good plan allows the writer to develop the different ideas in a way that will be clear to the reader. A good plan shows the interconnectedness of the different ideas in the paper. The plan of a paper at the beginning also helps the reader to know where the writer is going and to appreciate the relationship between the ideas even better. With the plan of an essay, EUCLID (2024, 9) believes that a plan helps the writer to “work out how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured.”

c) Stylistic presentation

What adds strength to an academic paper is how the ideas are presented. The author of the paper could have very great ideas, but if these ideas are poorly presented, the beauty of those ideas will not come out clearly. That is why, in an academic paper worthy of the name, the language of the text should be fluent and easily understood. The organization of the ideas should be coherent. A reader will find it easier to read a paper that shows logically the succession or evolution of the ideas. In that connection, the writing style of the academic paper should be consistent. The English grammatical rules should be well respected. Regarding grammar, the use of punctuation is of crucial importance. Punctuations help to give a particular tone and rhythm to the. The absence of simple

punctuation like a comma, a question mark, or even a period will affect the smooth understanding of the text. EUCLID (2024, 41) agree that a good stylistic presentation of an academic paper, in addition to the punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary, should also have good sentence lengths, font usage, good spellings, paragraphing, the use of headings, etc.

3) WEAKNESSES OF AN ACADEMIC PAPER

d) Plagiarism

In the world of science, there is hardly a new idea that has yet to be brought up by someone somewhere else. It is precisely for that reason that students are required to do research and know the existence of books and articles that have already been written on the subject. When that is done, intellectual honesty requires that the student attributes the idea to the original author. When the student fails to do that, we talk of plagiarism. According to EUCLID (2024, 34). "Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information." Some prominent examples of plagiarism are copying and pasting material from the internet without attributing the source to the author. Also, asking someone to help write a paper and putting one's name in it will be considered plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34).

Plagiarism weakens an academic paper because the writer needs to allow the reader to see the originality of their ideas and how they have developed them. The best way to avoid plagiarism is to write on a topic that one is passionate about. In this way, the writer can avoid the temptation of copying and pasting without verification. It will also be helpful to research the topic enough and make a clear distinction between borrowed information and one's own ideas.

e) Poor presentation

In the first part of this paper, I mentioned that the stylistic presentation of an academic paper matters. A good presentation adds to the strength of a paper. Conversely, a good presentation of the paper will strengthen the academic paper. By poor presentation, I mean a haphazard and poor organization of ideas. Lack of coherence and an illogical flow of ideas will create more confusion in the reader's minds. To avoid this weakness, EUCLID (2024, 11) offers some helpful advice as follows:

Each paragraph in the body of the essay should deal with one main point/ aspect of your answer.

Each paragraph should contain:

1. A topic sentence that states the main or controlling idea;
2. Supporting sentences to explain and develop the point you are making;

3. Most of the time, your point should be supported by some form of evidence from your reading or by an example drawn from the subject area; and
4. Finish off the paragraph with a critical conclusion you have drawn from the evidence.

4) WRITING OFF-TOPIC

One of the strengths of an academic essay is choosing a good topic and presenting it. However, when the writer of an essay does not follow a particular trend of thought that flows from the main topic, there is a possibility of digression or writing off-topic. This happens often when the writer needs to follow a writing plan. Butte College advises students that: “Your thesis statement is a promise to your reader about what you will cover in your paper. Do not write "off" this subject; do not include sentences that do not support or elaborate on this main idea.”

5) CONCLUSION

The above points that bring out the strengths and weaknesses of an academic paper prove that writing a good academic paper is a demanding task. It requires time and personal effort. Nevertheless, it is helpful to begin working on an academic paper early enough. Students who give themselves time to work on their academic papers will greatly improve their skills in subsequent papers.

REFERENCE LIST

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